

COMPOSITION OF METAL-CERAMIC FILTER FOR CLEANING GAS-AIR
FLOWS.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6050912>

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Annotation: A technology for obtaining metal powder-based metal-ceramic filters for the final stage of high-level treatment of gas-air discharge treatment systems of enterprises. The metal-ceramic filters completely restores the required capacity to clean the gas-air stream after re-cleaning. Accordingly, the technology showed that the heat resistance and efficiency of the filters are excellent.

Key words: metal-ceramic filters, gas-air flows, cleaning the gas

It is known that in the metallurgy, thermal power and chemical industries, waste gases are passed through a series of purification systems before being released into the atmosphere. However, in many cases, very small particles of from 10 to 1 μm in the exhaust gas-air streams are able to pass through the effluent treatment system [1]. One of the main reasons for this is the use of wire mesh filters in exhaust gas treatment systems [1].

The main disadvantage of grille filters is that they are produced by pouring 0.1 mm diameter wires to achieve a high degree of purification of gas-air streams. Wire-filled mesh filters are easily deformed even at low pressures of the gas-air stream, and as a result, the size of the cleaning cells gradually begins to open, causing some large particles to pass through the filter barrier [2].

Metal-ceramic filters developed by technological methods of powder metallurgy are free from such shortcomings and have high strength, corrosion resistance, heat resistance and high permeability [3,4]. Metal-ceramic filters are formed by pressing the powders of metals and alloys with special porous powders, forming them at high pressure and heating them in a protected atmosphere at a temperature of 1050-1200 °C [5].

We have developed a technology for obtaining metal powder-based metal-ceramic filters for the final stage of high-level treatment of gas-air discharge treatment systems of enterprises, and on the basis of this technology for SUE “MUBORAKNEFTEGAZ” the size of buffer gases with a temperature of 300 °C is from 50 to 10 microns. Metal-ceramic

filters were obtained from the particles. An overview of the filters obtained for “MUBORAKNEFTEGAZ” is shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1. Metal-ceramic filters.

The size of the obtained metal-ceramic filters is 320 mm in diameter and 120 mm in height. As a result of their stacking, the total height is 1.5 m and the wall thickness is 10 mm.

For the production of metal-ceramic filters, we have developed a technology for the production of iron powder by processing the iron-based waste (rolled metal) of Bekabad metallurgy as a raw material [3]. According to the developed technology, rolled metal is washed in water, and then dried at 500 °C, dried metal is crushed in ball mills, and crushed metal is sifted and prepared for recovery.

The powder of rolled metal, which has been prepared, is recovered with the help of hydrogen in special furnaces at a temperature of 700-750 °C. The recovered iron powder is pulverized in a ball mill to sift the powder needed to obtain the metal-ceramic filters and mixed with the porous powder to make the metal-ceramic filters.

For the preparation of metal-ceramic filters, a mixture of slag is prepared from iron powder. In addition to iron powder, the slag mixture consists of plasticizers and porous components. The main purpose of applying a plasticizer to iron powder is to increase the formation of iron powder under pressure in the press mold. Plasticizer iron powder allows easy (unbreakable) removal from the press molds after molding and retains its shape during baking. Typically, in powder metallurgy practice, iron powder is pressed and added to ferrous metal powder in a 1 % mass unit from a 10 % solution of rubber in gasoline to increase the rate of formation. The purpose of melting rubber in gasoline is to ensure that it mixes well with each iron powder particle.

The mixture, consisting of ferrous metal powder and plasticizer, was stirred for 3 hours in a container of the ChS-50L worm mixer and turned into a plastic mass. Drying of the finished mass of gasoline was carried out in a hermetically sealed drying oven model SNOL 21-5 at a temperature of 35-40 °C for 1-2 hours. After the slag mixture was dried on gasoline, the iron powder particles turned into a dry mass that stuck together through

the rubber. The mass of the dry slag mixture was pulverized on a DP-10L grinding machine and obtained a degree of compaction.

In order to increase the heat and corrosion resistance of metal-ceramic filters obtained on the basis of iron powder, the material was subjected to thermo diffusion alloying with 16% Cr, 12% Al and 8% Si [5].

The developed metal-ceramic filters were installed in the buffer gas treatment system of the Kokdumalak branch of the State Unitary Enterprise Muborakneftegaz. The total surface area of installed metal-ceramic filters was 1.07 m². A gas-air stream was sent to the metal-ceramic filter at a temperature of 110-380 °C and a pressure of 7 kgf/cm². The fresh gas-air flow pressure from the filtration unit was 6.7 kgf/cm², indicating the expected purification efficiency of 11,676 m³/h.

It was found that the metal-ceramic filter could clean the gas not only from particles but also from acidic vapors for 1 hour, because in the process of cleaning the gas, condensate droplets from the bottom of the metal-ceramic filter began to drip down the filter wall. A total of 116.76 g of liquid was collected in the condensate collector in 1 hour. The testing process lasted 6 months to determine the operational properties of metal-ceramic filters.

Tables 1 and 2 show the analysis of the gas-air flow that needs to be cleaned by the plant and cleaned by metal-ceramic filters provided by the plant's laboratory.

Table 1

Pre-cleaning analysis of gas-air flow

Gas-air temperature, °C	Particle size distribution, mg/m ³				
	condensate	till 50 mkm	from 50 to 5 mkm	from 25 to 10 mkm	less than 10 mkm
from 200 to 300	~1	0,02	2,2	2,75	1,5

Table 2

Filtered gas-air flow analysis

Gas-air temperature, °C	Particle size distribution, mg/m ³				
	condensate	till 50 mkm	from 50 to 5 mkm	from 25 to 10 mkm	less than 10 mkm
from 200 to 300	0	0	0	0	0

The pressure of the gas-air flow transferred to the metal-ceramic filter changed from 7 kgf/cm² to 7.7 kgf/cm² for 6 months, the outlet pressure of the purified gas-air flow from 6.7 kgf/cm² to 5.5 kgf/cm², productivity Changed from 11676 m³/h to 9584 m³/h.

The process was stopped and the metal-ceramic filters were removed. The outer and inner surfaces of the removed filters were examined with a magnifying glass. During a six-

month cleanup of the gas-air stream heated to 200–300 °C, particles were found to be trapped in 55–60 % of the porous holes on the outer surfaces of the filter, but no cracks or signs of oxidation were found on the outer and inner surfaces. To clean the metal-ceramic filters from particles, fresh airflow was sent to them at a speed of 200 m^3/min for 3 hours using a compressor in the opposite direction of filtration under a pressure of 9 kgf/cm^2 . In addition, the filters were subjected to ultrasound during the cleaning process. The cleaned filters were returned to the process and the heated gas-air stream continued to be cleaned.

The metal-ceramic filters completely restored the 11676 m^3/h capacity required to clean the gas-air stream after re-cleaning. Accordingly, the company rated the heat resistance and efficiency of the filters as excellent.

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